

IMPROVED PROCEDURES FOR THE DETERMINATION OF T_g BY DYNAMIC MECHANICAL ANALYSIS

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SUMMARY

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) is widely used for the measurement of T_g in composite materials. However, well-known thermal lag effects can result in incorrect reporting of the data and high variability between data obtained at different test sites. Reducing the scanning rate is not sufficient to remove the effect (especially for curing systems). An improved method for compensating for this effect is presented, aided by the development of a temperature reference specimen. The new procedure developed shows good repeatability. Based on this research, a new draft standard has been developed for T_g determination by DMA (ISO/CD 6721:11).

Keywords: dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), thermal analysis, glass transition temperature, temperature calibration

INTRODUCTION

Measurement of the glass transition temperature (T_g) provides important data that assist designers in the choice of material for their product related to the required service temperature. For composites fabricators and users, measurement of T_g can ensure that the material is correctly cured. Thermal analysis techniques, particularly Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) and Thermo Mechanical Analysis (TMA) have been widely used to determine the T_g of a material supporting the quality assurance (QA) process for material qualification and supply. All techniques make measurements of the material response while the sample is heated using a controlled temperature ramp profile, which is a built-in programmable feature in the control software of all commercially available instrumentation. Briefly the important aspects of these methods are:-

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

In a DSC experiment, T_g is denoted as the point of inflection in the step change observed in the heat flow curve [1]. There is concern that the small amount material (few milligrams) used in the test may not be representative of the overall component. The step change transition is not always clearly defined and the difficulty in interpretation is more evident in cured materials. The ratio of resin and fibre content can influence the sensitivity of the data generated as the fibre forms a large inert proportion of the specimen mass.

Thermo Mechanical Analysis (TMA)

In TMA, the dimensional changes in a material as a function of temperature, time and an applied force is measured. T_g is derived from the onset point [2-3] from either side

of the step transition during temperature ramping, which can be operator dependent and lead to inconsistent reporting, especially for composite materials.

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA)

DMA records the mechanical response (i.e. load and displacement) of a material as a function of temperature (time) while cycled at a single or multiple applied frequencies. DMA is a versatile technique that can be used in many deformation modes (e.g. tension, compression) and specimen formats (e.g. coupons, fibres) that are available in most commercial instrumentation. Measurements are undertaken at slower heating rates than in DSC (3 °C/min compared to 10 °C/min).

Figure 1: DMA trace for a simple material system

This technique has a choice of analysis points in several standards [4] and other test methods (e.g. company in-house) for T_g determination. The analysis points range from the transition onset or inflection point in the storage modulus (vs. temperature curve), the loss modulus peak or the tan delta peak. Previous research identified the inflection point in the storage modulus (linear scale) as the most consistent analysis point [5]. This temperature also generally agrees with the temperature at the peak value in the loss modulus curve (see Figure 1). Whilst the glass transition in a DMA trace is usually well defined, there has been concern expressed in the reported temperatures. This is due to several factors,

- Design of most commercially available instrumentation where the temperature sensor measures the oven environment around the specimen rather than the specimen itself. This leads to problems due to thermal lag between the specimen and the surrounding environment,
- The wide range of analysis points used to denote T_g . The differences between the onset of the storage modulus drop and tan delta peak could be as high as 40 °C,
- Choice of test parameters used (e.g. heating rate, frequency, deformation mode),
- Lack of a standardised temperature calibration method.

INITIAL INTERLABORATORY TRIAL

Interlaboratory tests were undertaken in previous research [5] for the measurement of T_g (Figure 2) for DMA and DSC using both reinforced and unreinforced plastics. It was found that whilst the repeatability (within site variability) of both the DMA and DSC techniques were good, the reproducibility (between site variability) of the DMA measurements was much poorer than for DSC (Tables 1 and 2). The heating rate, placement of the temperature sensor by the operator, instrument clamps, the design of the oven chamber and the size and thermal conductivity of the specimen itself are some of the contributory factors influencing the data generated by DMA. It was considered that the variability could be the result of errors in the specimen temperature measurement.

Figure 2: Interlaboratory test exercise – T_g determination using both DMA and DSC techniques for a polymeric material

Table 1: Precision data for DSC

[Repeatability = within site variability, Reproducibility = between site variability]

Material	Sites	Mean (°C)	Repeatability (°C)	Reproducibility (°C)
Unreinforced polyester	8	92.55	3.88	6.13
Glass fibre-polyester	7	92.79	3.69	11.03
Carbon fibre-epoxy	8	137.75	5.23	15.62
Epoxy adhesive	5	55.64	2.89	12.86

Table 2: Precision data for DMA

Material	Sites	Mean (°C)	Repeatability (°C)	Reproducibility (°C)
Unreinforced polyester	7	93.35	2.92	25.69
Glass fibre-polyester	7	98.62	5.94	24.52
Carbon fibre-epoxy	6	157.95	4.93	15.85
Epoxy adhesive	5	70.38	5.08	17.61

Tests at Multiple Heating Rates

A further series of tests were undertaken at several heating ramps from 1 to 10 °C/min. It was noted that results varied with heating rate and that the behaviour was different for reinforced material and unreinforced material (Figure 3), although the same cure schedule was used (i.e. the resin T_g should have been similar). However, there is also a difference in the thermal conductivity of the two types of material, with and without fibre reinforcement.

The results suggest that thermal lag could be responsible for the differences and trends observed, especially as there was no significant variation for the much smaller DSC sample (a few milligrams).

Figure 3: DMA and DSC tests on material specimens with and without reinforced fibres indicating heating rate response

Temperature Lag Response in a DMA

To assess the significance of the thermal lag problem, a composite specimen was loaded in the instrument with a conventional temperature sensor (thermocouple) placed in the specimen through a hole drilled through to the centre of the specimen (Figure 4). The temperature responses were monitored along with the instrument built-in temperature (oven) readout while the specimen was heated using a controlled ramp.

Figure 4: Temperature monitoring for the specimen centre relative to the instrument readout

It was evident that at the stable state ambient condition, there was no significant difference between the readings. Once the heating commenced, the differences in temperature across the specimen under test in a DMA is highlighted. In this case, at the apparent T_g measured at $3\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, the specimen internal temperature was $6\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than the instrument readout.

DEVELOPMENT OF A TEMPERATURE REFERENCE SPECIMEN

Preliminary trials on different carrier materials to embed indium were tried before choosing a woven carbon fibre prepreg. The T_g of this material was higher than the melting point of indium.

Tests were undertaken to analyse the response related to the melting of the indium within the specimens. Initial trials in oven-cured prototypes with different configurations proved to be successful. Based on the results, the most suitable configuration was adopted and a batch of specimens was manufactured in an autoclave. Test specimens were then machined to the required dimensions replicating a typical DMA flexure bar geometry laminate specimen and tested at different heating rates. The

melting point of the indium was indicated by a sudden drop in the loss modulus data. The peak in loss modulus values were plotted against the heating rate. The “apparent” melt temperature varied for the tests at the different heating rates (Figure 5). The zero degree-heating rate was determined by linearly extrapolating the analysis point at the different heating rates.

Figure 5: Example of signal response using the temperature reference specimen for the melting of indium at different heating rates

Measurement was also carried out at multiple heating rates on a plain carbon fibre-reinforced plastic (CFRP) specimen. The zero degree heating rate value thus extrapolated was 192 °C, which was around 35 °C above the reference indium melting point (156.6 °C). This eliminated the possibility of detecting overlapping transitions (i.e. indium melt and the T_g of the composite) when used as a temperature reference specimen with indium encapsulated.

SECOND INTERLABORATORY TEST EXERCISE

The usability of the reference specimen on instrumentation from different suppliers and models had to be tested. An interlaboratory trial was conducted as part of current research. The objective of the exercise was to establish the performance of the reference specimens in order to assess the variability in the results irrespective of the instrumentation used. The exercise used instruments from four different suppliers and five different models. Data also included tests from both the single cantilever bending and torsion modes using bar geometry specimens. The results from the interlaboratory trial are presented below.

Test protocol

The participants were provided a reference specimen from the first batch of manufactured specimens, along with a template for reporting of the data. The task involved undertaking measurements at multiple heating rates following a draft procedure. Tests were conducted at multiple heating rates of 10, 5, 3 and 1 °C/min.

Data analysis used the sharp deviation in the loss modulus curve related to the melting of indium. Figure 5 indicates an example of the type of responses expected for the melting of indium at the different heating rates. This could vary depending on instrumentation used. The analysed data point for the different heating rate was then plotted heating rate vs. indium melting point. The zero degree heating rate value is subsequently obtained by extrapolation.

Results of the Interlaboratory Test Exercise

Figure 6: results from interlaboratory test exercise

Indium melting point analysis (* based on 7 sets of data)

Average 0 °C/min heating rate value = 157.2 °C
Average deviation from reference value (156.6 °C) = 0.9 °C
Standard Deviation = 0.83 °C

Discussion of Results

The majority of the specimens performed as expected and 7 sets of results are presented in Figure 6 labelled as site 1 to 7. The results both indicated the varying temperature sensitivity of different equipment and the consistency of the extrapolated values. The data also provides confirmation of the thermocouple operation/calibration. (N.B. thermocouple also checked at the ambient temperature).

REVISED GLASS TRANSITION MEASUREMENT PROCEDURE

Based on the findings of the interlaboratory trials, a new procedure was developed for potential standardisation of measurements made using DMA equipment.

Step 1 - Instrument Temperature Response

The heating rate dependency of the instrument is initially established by testing the temperature reference specimen at multiple heating rates, or by testing the actual test material. If the instrument has no heating rate variability on scanning the temperature reference specimen, a standard (e.g. 3 °C/min) heating rate can be used. If the instrument response indicates heating rate dependency, one of two approaches described below in steps 2 and 3 should be followed.

Step 2 - T_g (Reference)

Measurement of the apparent T_g is obtained at several heating rates using new test specimens for each measurement and the T_g determined at the zero heating rate value (Figure 7) extrapolated as previously described. Measurements are undertaken at a (common/standard) frequency of 1 Hz.

Figure 7: DMA data for different heating rates for a composite material (T_g analysis on the inflection point of the storage modulus curve)

Step 3 – Qualification Data - T_g (QA)

Using the calibration curve developed in Step 2, as in Figure 7, developed from the multiple heating rate values of the material specimen. Subsequent material test specimens can be tested at either 3 or 5 °C/min and the offset for that temperature applied to report the T_g value (Figure 8). A faster heating rate of 10 °C/min, 20 °C/min or higher can also be used with appropriate values offset temperature X.

An illustration of the approach is indicated in Figure 8. The offset (temperature X °C) to determine the T_g (QA) is determined from the calibration curve. The offset temperature can vary depending on instrumentation used, but will be set for each case (i.e. combination of equipment, material and test condition) by the corresponding calibration curve.

Figure 8: Offset applied for determination of T_g at a particular heating rate (5 °C per minute heating rate as illustrated)

CONCLUSIONS

The research reported in this paper has demonstrated that there is a significant effect of thermal lag on the T_g measured by DMA. This may have resulted in all current data generated by existing test methods to be incorrect (i.e. too high). Reducing the scanning rate is not sufficient to remove the effect (especially for materials additionally curing during the test). The new procedure developed shows good repeatability. Based on this research, a new draft standard has been proposed for T_g determination by DMA (ISO/CD 6721:11).

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